

Potential reduction of the inertial mass of tuned vibration absorbers by means of mechanical impedance matching

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 16 August 2017

Received in revised form 19 September 2018

Accepted 22 October 2018

Available online 2 November 2018

Handling Editor: H. Ouyang

Keywords:

Tuned mass damper

Vibration absorber

Dynamics

Passive damping

Structural damping

Magnetic

Mechanical design

Impedance matching

ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new technology for vibration isolation based on impedance matching using a linear magnetic gear is presented. Using that operational principle, a prototype of an Impedance Matching Tuned Vibration Absorber (Z-TVA) is designed, manufactured and tested. An inertial mass is coupled to the fast-moving stage of the linear magnetic gear, increasing its motion proportionally to the square of the gear ratio, and therefore its effectiveness as a vibration absorber.

A theoretical model is postulated and validated with tests at a component level, demonstrating a promising solution for drastically reducing the required mass and installation and maintenance cost. A potential reduction of the required mass of a vibration absorber of more than an order of magnitude is predicted.

1. Introduction

Minimization of vibrations on structures is a frequent requirement in many engineering fields. One of the possible strategies to reduce vibrations, when the excitation frequencies are well-known, is to store part of the vibration energy by means of a Tuned Vibration Absorber (TVA) [1]. This solution is widely used in seismic protection of buildings and other structures [2], to minimize vibrations in aircrafts [3], satellites and helicopters [4], in wind turbines [5], for energy harvesting optimization [6] or even to compensate rotor unbalances in washing machines [7].

The main parameter that describes a TVA performance is the inertial mass of the absorber [8]. In order to enhance the effectiveness of the classical TVA, its mass has to be increased. However, increasing the inertial mass involves technical and economic drawbacks like increasing the envelope of the device or the costs of installation and maintenance. Therefore, a reduction of the mass is highly desirable for any application [9].

In order to reduce the required inertial mass of a TVA without decreasing its performance as a vibration isolation device, a novel solution based on motion amplification and impedance matching by a linear magnetic gear is proposed in this paper. A linear magnetic gear connected to a properly tuned internal mass acts as a motion amplification device (more properly,

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mechanical impedance matching). Mechanical impedance matching of a linear magnetic gear is discussed in Ref. [10]. This drastically reduces the overall required mass of the system and potentially saves space and costs.

During this research, in the framework of the FP7 Clean Sky Z-Damper project, we have designed, manufactured and experimentally demonstrated a Tuned Vibration Absorber based on the Z-Damper technology [11] (Z-TVA). The technology potentially offers high space and mass savings compared to a classic TVA of equivalent performance. Experimental tests at component level are presented and the results discussed. Finally, a theoretical case study is developed focused in the vibration suppression of an aircraft engine. The theoretical behavior of the system with a Z-TVA is compared with the behavior of a classic TVA in terms of performance and weight.

2. Theoretical description

2.1. Magnetic gearbox operational principle

Magnetic devices and mechanisms such as bearings [12], dampers [13,14], positioning mechanisms [15], gears [16,17] or torque limiters [18] are increasingly being used instead of classic mechanical devices. Their potential advantages include the elimination of wear and lubrication, improvement of the reliability and reduction of the generated noise. For these reasons, they are drawing increasing attention in many engineering fields such as aerospace [19,20], transportation [21] or energy harvesting [22].

Magnetic gears can be built in rotatory or linear configurations. Operational principle of such gears is very similar and is widely discussed in Refs. [10,23]. A linear magnetic gear is mainly composed of three stages: a slow moving stage, a fast moving stage and a stator. For the gear presented in this paper, the slow moving stage can be considered as the input of the device and will be connected to the source of vibrations. The input stage is mainly composed of a set of soft magnetic teeth. The stator and the fast stage are mainly composed of permanent magnets. During the motion of the gear, the soft magnetic teeth are magnetized by the fast stage permanent magnets so they tend to align with the stator magnets. As a result of the magnetic interactions, the motion of the fast stage is amplified. The relationship between the input and fast stage displacement amplitudes, in quasi-static conditions, can be defined as:

$$x_f = n \cdot x_i \quad (1)$$

where

x_i is the linear input displacement,
 x_f is the fast stage displacement,
 n is the gear ratio

Fig. 1 schematizes the motion of the different stages in a linear magnetic gear. The displacement amplification is typically indicated by the gear ratio (n), and it is defined similarly to a mechanical gears. It just depends on the number of permanent magnets in the stator (N_0) and soft magnetic teeth in the input stage (N_s) that are involved in the gearing [11]. Eq. (2) is used to calculate the gear ratio in a magnetic gear:

Fig. 1. Magnetic linear gear motion amplification concept.

$$n = \frac{N_o}{N_o - N_s} \quad (2)$$

In order to preserve the energy conservation principle, a relationship between the forces exerted by the input, fast stage and stator can be defined too:

$$F_i = -n \cdot F_f \text{ and } F_s = (n - 1) \cdot F_f \quad (3)$$

where

F_i is the linear input force,
 F_f is the fast stage force.

The impedances of the input and fast moving stage can be derived from previous equation as:

$$Z_i = \frac{F_f}{x_i} \text{ and } Z_f = \frac{F_f}{x_f} \quad (4)$$

where

Z_i and Z_f are the input and fast stage impedance respectively,
 x_i and x_f are the input and fast stage velocity respectively.

Finally, impedance matching between the input and the fast moving stage can be defined as:

$$Z_i = n^2 Z_f \quad (5)$$

A relevant feature of the technology is that the force that a magnetic gear can exert depends upon the linear shift between the stages of the gear with regard to the equilibrium position ($F=0$). This is very well represented when an infinite impedance (perfect brake) is coupled to the fast moving stage and an input motion is forced. Fig. 2 shows the normalized force (ratio between the measured force and the maximum gear force) vs. the linear displacement of the input stage.

From the previous figure, two very relevant features can be observed. First, there is a maximum load capacity of the gear. If this force is exceeded, the input stage will just slide smoothly to the next stable region of the gear. This inherent self-protection capability against overloads acts as a mechanical resettable fuse that protects not only the gear but also all the other elements in the kinematic chain.

Fig. 2. Normalized force vs. axial displacement of the linear gear in lock situation.

Second, the force exerted by the device depends on the axial displacement of the input stage of the gear. Moreover, a certain force is exerted since the very beginning of the movement. For reciprocating motion like vibrations, there is virtually zero-backlash present in the device. This is not the situation of classic mechanical gears which present backlash that causes clearance and non-linearity behaviors [24] that are detrimental for the performance of the device.

2.2. Device internal dynamic equations

When masses, stiffness and damping parameters of the gearbox are considered, a more detailed model is required to describe the dynamic behavior of the Z-TVA. Fig. 3 shows a diagram of the Z-TVA internal model and how it is connected to the vibrating mass (m) when acting as a vibration absorber.

In Fig. 3b), an equivalent dynamic diagram of the Z-TVA is proposed. The black body represents the input or slow-moving stage (1), which is rigidly connected to the vibrating mass (m). The stator of the Z-TVA (2), is also rigidly connected to the ground (3). A "virtual intermediate stage" (4), located inside the gearbox, is defined to assist the theoretical description of the device and the interpretation of the proposed model.

This "virtual intermediate stage" presents a perfect displacement multiplication ($n \cdot x$) with regard to the input stage displacement (x). An inertial mass (m_a) is magnetically coupled to the "virtual intermediate stage" by an equivalent spring of stiffness (k_a). The magnetic equivalent stiffness will be only acting when a relative displacement from the virtual stage and the inertial mass is induced. This relative displacement can be caused by internal forces (inertia) or by any external force like damping.

Main contribution to damping is generated by eddy current dissipations inside the device. It is well known, that for low frequencies, eddy current damping is of the viscous type [25]. Therefore the damping force is proportional to the speed of the Z-TVA mass (m_a). An equivalent viscous damping coefficient (c_a) can be defined related to the relative speed of the inertial mass and the stator of the device.

It has to be noted that those couplings or connection between stages inside the Z-TVA are based on contactless magnetic interactions and the physical contact in the representation of k_a and c_a in Fig. 3 are only intended to assist the interpretation of the model.

Based on the previous model for the Z-TVA, the motion equation for the inertial mass (m_a). can be defined as:

$$m_a \ddot{x}_a + k_a(x_a - nx) + c_a \dot{x}_a = 0 \quad (6)$$

The normalized displacement (ND) or displacement ratio between the fast moving stage (x_a) and (n) times the input forced harmonic excitation (x) can be written as:

$$ND = \frac{x_a}{n \cdot x} = \frac{k_a}{(k_a - m_a \omega^2) + j c_a \omega}$$

where

ω is the frequency of the harmonic excitation.

Fig. 3. a) Z-TVA connected to a vibrating mass (left); b) Z-TVA dynamic internal model (right).

And therefore the relationship of the Z-TVA mass (m_a) and the main mass displacement (m) as a function of the excitation frequency can be defined as:

$$x_a = nx \cdot \frac{1}{(1 - \Omega_a^2) + j2\xi_a\Omega_a} \quad (8)$$

where

ξ_a is the damping ratio of the Z-TVA defined as:

$$\xi_a = \frac{c_a}{2\sqrt{k_a \cdot m_a}} \quad (9)$$

where

Ω_a is the frequency ratio of the Z-TVA defined as:

$$\Omega_a = \frac{\Omega}{\Omega_a} \quad (10)$$

where

Ω_a is the fast moving stage natural frequency.

The magnetic forces acting on the fast-inertial mass (F_f) can be expressed as a function of the elastic deformation of the "magnetic spring" (k_a) as:

$$F_f = -k_a(x_a - nx) \quad (11)$$

Using the expression of x_a in eq. (8), the fast stage force can be expressed in the frequency domain, as:

$$F_f = -nk_a x \cdot \frac{\Omega_a^2 - j2\xi_a\Omega_a}{(1 - \Omega_a^2) + j2\xi_a\Omega_a} \quad (12)$$

By hypothesis of the linear magnetic gearbox, the Z-TVA reactive force (F_Z) exerted by the device when connected to the main system mass (m) is multiplied by the gearbox ratio.

Therefore, combining eq. (3) and eq. (12).

$$F_Z = n^2 k_a x \left[\frac{\Omega_a^2 - j2\xi_a\Omega_a}{(1 - \Omega_a^2) + j2\xi_a\Omega_a} \right] \quad (13)$$

Then the amplitude $|F_Z|$ of the Z-TVA response can be calculated as:

$$|F_Z| = |n^2 k_a x| \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\Omega^4 + (2\xi_a\Omega_a)^2}{(1 - \Omega^2)^2 + (2\xi_a\Omega)^2}} \quad (14)$$

In order to guide the linear motion of the different stages of the gear, a set of linear bearings are used as it will be further detailed in next sections. Friction bearings are used between the slow moving stage and the stator of the Z-TVA. In order to represent the friction observed during tests, a Coulomb friction force is included in eq. (15). The measured amplitude of the Z-TVA input force can be approximated to:

$$|F_Z| = |n^2 k_a x| \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\Omega^4 + (2\xi_a \Omega)^2}{(1 - \Omega^2)^2 + (2\xi_a \Omega)^2}} + |F_c| \quad 2 \quad (15)$$

where

F_c is the Coulomb equivalent force.

2.3. Theoretical model of the Z-Tuned vibration absorber

The performance of the device as a Tuned Vibration Absorber when connected to a mass vibrating by the action of an external harmonic force has been evaluated in this section.

In a classic TVA, the main system mass is connected to the ground by an equivalent stiffness and damper, that is assumed of the viscous type for the purpose of this paper. Additionally, the mass is connected to the inertial mass of the tuned vibration absorber by a properly tuned stiffness and a damper. Both, stiffness and damping, have to be properly designed to isolate the desired resonance of the system.

Similarly, on the Z-TVA, the system mass is connected by a spring (k) and a viscous damper (c) to the ground. Internally, the Z-TVA has properly tuned magnetic stiffness (k_a) and damping (c_a), which allows the inertial mass (m_a) to resonate at the desired frequency. This inertial mass is connected to or integrated in the fast-moving stage of the gearbox. However, on the contrary to a classic TVA, the stator of the Z-TVA needs to be connected directly to the ground, as shown in Fig. 3.

The 2DoF system shown in Fig. 3a can be described by the motion equations of the mass (m) and the inertial mass (m_a):

$$\begin{bmatrix} m & 0 \\ 0 & m_a \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{x}_a \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} c & 0 \\ 0 & c_a \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{x}_a \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} k + n^2 k_a & -n k_a \\ -n k_a & k_a \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x \\ x_a \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F_e \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

The natural frequencies of the main system can be defined as:

$$\omega_m = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} \quad (17)$$

By solving eq. (16), F_e can be obtained. Then, the normalized displacement amplitude $\frac{XK}{F_e}$ of the main mass (m) can be expressed as:

$$\left| \frac{XK}{F_e} \right| = \sqrt{\frac{\left(1 - \frac{\Omega_m^2}{\beta^2}\right)^2 + \left(2\xi_a \frac{\Omega_m^2}{\beta}\right)^2}{\left(\frac{\Omega_m^4}{\beta^2} - \left(\frac{4\xi_a \xi_p}{\beta} + \frac{1}{\beta^2} + (n^2 \mu + 1)\right) \Omega_m^2 + 1\right)^2 + 4\left(\Omega_m^2 \left(\frac{\xi_a}{\beta} + \xi_p + n^2 \beta \mu \xi_a\right) - \frac{\Omega_m^2}{\beta} \left(\xi_a + \frac{\xi_p}{\beta}\right)\right)^2}} \quad (18)$$

where

μ is the mass ratio of the absorber defined as $\mu = \frac{m_a}{m}$,

Ω_m is the frequency ratio between excitation and natural frequencies $\Omega_m = \frac{\omega}{\omega_m}$,

β is the ratio between the natural frequencies of the Z-TVA and the main mass $\beta = \frac{\omega_a}{\omega_m}$,

ξ_a and ξ_p are the TVA and the structural damping ratios $\xi_a = \frac{c_a}{2\sqrt{k_a \cdot m_a}}$ and $\xi_p = \frac{c}{2\sqrt{k \cdot m}}$.

Because the Z-TVA is also connected to the ground, the force transmissibility may differ from that one of a classic TVA, which only present connection to the ground through the main stiffness (k) and damper (c). In the case of the Z-TVA, transmissibility of forces can be expressed in the time domain as:

$$T_Z = \frac{F_t}{F_e} = \frac{k \cdot x + c \cdot \dot{x} + F_Z}{F_e} \quad (19)$$

where

F_t is the force transmitted to the base.

By solving the previous equation in the frequency domain, the transmissibility of the Z-TVA can be calculated as:

$$T_z = \frac{(1 + j(2\xi_p \Omega_m)) \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{\Omega_m^2}{\beta^2} \right) + j(2\xi_a \frac{\Omega_m}{\beta}) \right) - n^2 \beta \mu \cdot \left(\frac{\Omega_m^2}{\beta^2} - j(2\xi_a \frac{\Omega_m}{\beta}) \right)}{\left(\left(1 - \Omega_m^2 \right) + j(2\xi_p \Omega_m) \right) \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{\Omega_m^2}{\beta^2} \right) + j(2\xi_a \frac{\Omega_m}{\beta}) \right) - n^2 \beta \mu \cdot \left(\frac{\Omega_m^2}{\beta^2} - j(2\xi_a \frac{\Omega_m}{\beta}) \right)} \quad (20)$$

The module of the transmissibility of forces of the Z-TVA to the ground ($|T_z|$) is depicted in eq. (21):

$$|T_z| = \sqrt{\frac{\left(1 - \left(\frac{4\xi_a \xi_p}{\beta} + \frac{1}{\beta^2} + n^2 \mu \right) \Omega_m^2 \right)^2 + 4 \left(\Omega_m \left(\frac{\xi_p}{\beta} + \xi_p + n^2 \beta \mu \xi_a \right) - \frac{\Omega_m^3}{\beta^2} (\xi_p) \right)^2}{\left(\frac{\Omega_m^4}{\beta^2} - \left(\frac{4\xi_a \xi_p}{\beta} + \frac{1}{\beta^2} + (n^2 \mu + 1) \right) \Omega_m^2 + 1 \right)^2 + 4 \left(\Omega_m \left(\frac{\xi_p}{\beta} + \xi_p + n^2 \beta \mu \xi_a \right) - \frac{\Omega_m^3}{\beta} \left(\xi_a + \frac{\xi_p}{\beta} \right) \right)^2}} \quad (21)$$

In order to compare the behavior of the Z-TVA, transmissibility of a classic TVA ($|T_c|$), described in eq. (22), is considered.

$$|T_c| = \sqrt{\frac{\left(1 - \left(\frac{4\xi_a \xi_p}{\beta} + \frac{1}{\beta^2} \right) \Omega_m^2 \right)^2 + 4 \left(\Omega_m \left(\frac{\xi_p}{\beta} + \xi_p \right) - \frac{\Omega_m^3}{\beta^2} (\xi_p) \right)^2}{\left(\frac{\Omega_m^4}{\beta^2} - \left(\frac{4\xi_a \xi_p}{\beta} + \frac{1}{\beta^2} + (\mu + 1) \right) \Omega_m^2 + 1 \right)^2 + 4 \left(\Omega_m \left(\frac{\xi_p}{\beta} + \xi_p + \beta \mu \xi_a \right) - \frac{\Omega_m^3}{\beta} \left(\xi_a + \frac{\xi_p}{\beta} \right) \right)^2}} \quad (22)$$

2.4. Theoretical case study

In order to compare the performance of the Z-TVA with a classic tuned vibration absorber, a theoretical case study is hypothesized. A vibrating mass of 5 tons is considered, similar to the new CROR engine of the SFWA concept in the FP7 Clean Sky research program [26], which has founded part of this research. The mass of the engine is estimated in about 5 tons. A representative equivalent stiffness (k) of the engine mount of $4.8 \times 10^7 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$ and a structural damping ratio of 1% are considered. A resonant frequency of interest to be isolated is identified in 18 Hz for this case study. Then, a classic TVA and a Z-TVA are designed and the transmissibility of vibrations and the normalized displacement of the motor compared.

The normalized displacement amplitude of the steady state response of the primary mass for a classic TVA is obtained from Ref. [8]. Optimal damping and frequency ratio have been derived using the equal-peak method developed by Den Hartog [27] and Brock [28]. Using this method, optimization of different characteristics of the transfer functions can be achieved [8,29]. In this work, we focus the optimization of damping and frequency ratio to achieve equal maximum peaks in the normalized displacement function. Optimal damping and frequency ratio for the Z-TVA can be defined as:

$$\beta^{\text{opt}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - n^2 \mu}} \quad \text{and} \quad \xi_a^{\text{opt}} = \frac{n}{2} \sqrt{\frac{3n^2 \mu}{2 - n^2 \mu}} \quad (23)$$

The main descriptive parameters of both absorbers are defined in Table 1.

Fig. 4 compares the theoretical normalized displacement amplitude of a classic TVA, Z-TVA and a system with no absorber but just structural damping.

It can be stated from Fig. 4 that the performance is very similar in terms of vibration suppression for both, the Z-TVA and the classic TVA.

Additionally, the vibration transmissibility is compared for the classic TVA and the Z-TVA. Fig. 5 represent the force transmissibility to the ground for both systems:

Table 1
Parameters for the classic TVA and Z-TVA used in the theoretical case study.

Parameter	Classic TVA	Z-TVA	Unit
Inertial mass, (m_o)	161.7	3.3	kg
Death weight	e	6	kg
Total weight	161.7	9.3	kg
Mass ratio, (m)	0.032	0.00066	e
Gearbox ratio, (n)	e	7	e
Optimal Damping, (ξ_o^{opt})	0.11	0.111	e
Optimal natural frequencies ratio, (b^{opt})	0.969	1.016	e

Fig. 4. Comparison of the theoretical normalized displacement of a classic optimal TVA and Z-TVA.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the theoretical transmissibility of a classic TVA and Z-TVA.

Note that, despite the Z-TVA is connected also to the ground, transmissibility of forces is not significantly affected and at higher frequencies than the resonance, the Z-TVA almost perfectly meets the transmissibility curve of a classic TVA. Moreover, the maximum value of the transmitted force is even reduced, providing an additional advantage for the technology in this particular application case. Both results theoretically demonstrate that the Z-TVA technology has the potential to provide similar or even improved vibration suppression but with a very significant weight saving. For evaluation of the mass saving of the Z-TVA we have considered that Z-TVA structural elements (stator, input, bearings, etc ...) contribute significantly to the overall weight of the device. Therefore, the whole mass of the Z-TVA is to be considered for comparison of the mass of the TVA and Z-TVA:

In summary, there are some significant advantages of using a linear magnetic gearbox for impedance matching in a TVA, potentially:

- 1) The impedance matching effect is used in the Z-TVA to multiply the acceleration of the inertial mass of a tuned vibration absorber therefore reducing the overall weight and the envelope of the system.
- 2) A linear magnetic gearbox does not present backlash so it can be used even with very low amplitude input vibrations, such as micro or sub-mm vibrations [30].
- 3) They do not need lubrication to operate, therefore reducing maintenance costs and increasing the temperature range for operation.

3. Z-TVA demonstrator

3.1. Prototype description

A prototype of a Z-TVA was designed, manufactured and tested at component level. The device is mainly composed of a linear magnetic gear with three stages: an input or slow moving stage, a fast moving stage, and the stator.

The fast moving stage is free to move inside the gearbox. The own mass of the fast stage acts as the inertial mass of the Z-TVA. The gearbox has been designed with a gear ratio $n = 7$ and a resonant frequency at about 18 Hz.

The stator and the fast moving stage are mainly composed of Nd₂Fe₁₄B N48H ring permanent magnets axially magnetized. The magnets in the stator are contained in a titanium grade 5 finned housing. Those fins improve the heat dissipation to the environment. Fast moving stage permanent magnets are assembled in a titanium grade 5 shaft.

All permanent magnets are placed with facing opposing polarities one another and kept in position using epoxy adhesives and mechanical fixtures. Magnetic flux concentrators are used in between the permanent magnets to improve the force capacity or stall force of the device about a 10%. They are made of 1 mm thickness steel AISI 1010 rings placed coaxially with the magnets.

The input stage is mainly composed of low carbon steel AISI 1010 laminated soft magnetic teeth. They are assembled inside a titanium grade 5 seamless tube. Non-magnetic titanium spacers, 5 mm in thickness, are used for an optimum disposition of the soft magnetic teeth in the magnetic gearbox.

Two grease lubricated linear ball bearings are used to allow relative motion between the fast moving stage and the input stage. Two grease lubricated Teflon bushings are used between the stator and the input stage. In both cases, the bearings are placed at each end of the stroke of the device. In order to connect the device to the actuator, a self-lubricated spherical rod ends from ISB model TSM 12C is used. Connection to the ground is done using the standard mechanical flanges seen in Fig. 6.

Most of the rest of the structural components of the device are manufactured in titanium grade 5 due to its high yield strength and low density. Fig. 6 shows a partial cross section of the device:

Main characteristics and figures of the performance of the device are summarized in Table 2.

3.2. Experimental test set-up

The objective of the test campaign presented in this paper has been to validate the performance of the Z-TVA at a component level. In order to characterize the behavior of the Z-TVA, a dedicated test bench was set-up. The test bench has been designed with an actuation bandwidth from 0 to about 60 Hz in a temperature controlled environment. The test bench is mainly composed by a MOOG Hydrodynamic Servo-Hydraulic Actuator (3) with a maximum force of 15 kN at 15 Hz and a maximum quasi-static stroke of 50 mm. The actuator is fed with ISO grade 32 oil pumped by the hydraulic group (4) equipped with a 15CV electric motor. The actuator is mounted on the bottom of a metallic structural support (1). This structural support has been specifically designed to minimize to minimize transmissibility to the ground and to minimize amplification of the input vibrations due to internal resonances of the structure. No modes below 200 Hz are present in the testbench.

The position of the actuator (input position) is measured by a non-contact LVDT 25 mm stroke sensor. The input force exerted by the actuator is measured by a 0.02 precision class HBM U10M traction-compression load cell with a measurement range up to 25 kN. The position of the fast stage inside the Z-TVA is characterized by a laser positioning sensor from Micro-Epsilon model optoNCDT ILD-1420 with 100 mm measurement range and a repeatability of 4 μm. Fig. 7 shows a picture of the test bench:

A thermally isolated climatic chamber (5), with an external metallic frame made in non-magnetic stainless steel 316L, is installed on top of the metallic bedplate of the test bench. A 4 kW centrifugal fan (6) of the 400 °C/2 h type is used to circulate the ventilation air inside the flexible high temperature resistant ducts. A 12 kW heat resistor plus a solid state controlled rectifier (7) allows a precise stabilization of the environmental temperature inside the climatic chamber using commercial PID controller. Multiple resistive temperature sensors (PT-100 and PT-1000) are used to monitor and control the temperature of the circulating air and the prototype itself. The speed and pressure of the ventilation air is measured at the entry of the

Fig. 6. Z-TVA manufactured prototype (top) and partial cross section (bottom).

Table 2
Main characteristics of the Z-TVA prototype.

Z-TVA			
Property	Value	Unit	
Diameter	82	mm	
Length	493	mm	
Total Weight	9.3	kg	
Z-TVA weight, (m_a)	3.3	kg	
Maximum input displacement [mm]	$>\pm 5$	mm	
Multiplication ratio, (n)	7:1		
Max. Transmittable Force (15 °C)	4670	N	
Temperature sensitivity	-2.9	N/°C	
Temperature range of use (experimentally validated)	[RT;95]	°C	
Natural frequency TVA	18 ± 1	Hz	
Input maximum stiffness	2080 ± 10	Nmm ⁻¹	
Fast stage stiffness, (k_a)	45 ± 2	Nmm ⁻¹	

climatic chamber by a Kimo MP 120S Anemometer equipped with a high temperature resistant Pitot tube. Finally, the data acquisition system (8) is composed of two NI 9217, one NI 9203, and one NI 9263 acquisition board mounted in an NI9188 rack.

3.2.1. Test procedure

To characterize the behavior of the Z-TVA at different temperatures and operational conditions, a set of static and dynamic characterization tests were carried out.

3.2.1.1. Quasi-static tests. Quasi-static tests were carried out first. The objective of these tests has been to obtain the input and fast stage stiffness, to measure the gear ratio and to obtain the sensitivity of the force capacity (or stall force) of the device to the environment temperature. For these tests, the fast stage motion was impeded by rigidly connecting the fast moving stage to the top load cell. In this “lock situation”, the impedance on the fast stage shaft can be considered infinite at all practical

Fig. 7. Testbench used for characterization of the Z-TVA.

means. Then, the heat and ventilation system is switch on and the temperature of the climatic chamber and the prototype controlled.

The prototype was tested in a range from room temperature to up to 90 °C degrees. Once the temperature is stable, a quasi-static sinusoidal motion is induced in the input shaft in a range from about 9 mm peak to peak with regard to the central equilibrium position of the device. Input position and forces in the input and fast-moving stage are measured. The process is repeated at different temperatures. Fig. 8 shows the test set up for the static characterization.

3.2.1.2. Dynamic tests. After the static characterization tests, the Z-TVA has been characterized for sinusoidal harmonic excitations at different frequencies. First, the rigid connection to the ground of the Z-TVA fast stage is eliminated, leaving the fast stage free to move. The own mass of the fast stage acts as the inertial mass (m_a) of the vibration absorber. The displacement of the input stage and the fast-moving stage are characterized and the input force measured. Fig. 9 shows the experimental set-up of the test bench for dynamic tests:

4. Experimental results

4.1. Static test results

Fig. 10 represents the input and output force vs. input displacement at room temperature according to the test procedure described in the previous section. Experimental data and predicted FEM magneto-static calculations are depicted in the figure.

It can be clearly observed that a significant hysteresis is observed in the force response of the input stage. This is very likely motivated by the friction damping generated in the bushing of the Z-TVA input stage. Despite the fact that this hysteretic behavior provides some level of damping required for the Z-TVA to operate, it potentially generates undesired wear of the bushings and hot spots and can introduce delays and errors in position control tasks [31]. Future developments may avoid friction damping in the bearings and achieve the required damping by other means like for example, eddy current damping.

Since the fast moving stage is equipped with ball bearings (with a much lower friction coefficient), the hysteretic damping in the fast stage is drastically reduced.

By combination of eq. (1) and eq. (3), a relationship between the input and fast stage stiffness can be defined as:

$$n^2 = \frac{k_i}{k_a} \quad (24)$$

Fig. 8. Z-TVA set up for static characterization.

The maximum fast moving stage stiffness can be calculated from data in Fig. 10 and is equal to $45 \pm 2 \text{ kNm}^{-1}$. Maximum stiffness of the input stage is calculated in $2080 \pm 10 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$. Using eq. (24), a gear ratio of 6.8 ± 0.8 can be calculated in good agreement with the simulation results.

The maximum transmittable force (input force before magnetic slip occurs) is experimentally verified at different temperatures. Fig. 11 show gear ratio (n) and maximum transmittable force (or stall force) vs. temperature. The lower the temperature, the higher the stall force.

4.2. Dynamic tests results

Input and output position vs. time for a sinusoidal input excitation of 4.7 mm amplitude and of frequencies from 0.1 to 5 Hz are represented in the Fig. 12. Tests were performed at room temperature. The multiplication of the input displacement is evident and of magnitude about 7 in very good agreement with the theoretical predictions.

Figs. 13 and 14 show the input and output speed and acceleration. Again, both are related by the gearbox ratio. It has to be noticed that the acceleration suddenly goes to zero when motion direction is inverted. This is probably caused by a small clearance in the kinematic spherical joints used to connect the input shaft with the hydraulic actuator rod.

Information of the behavior of the Z-TVA under harmonic sinusoidal excitations in a frequency bandwidth from 0.5 to 50 Hz is represented in the figure below for an input sinusoidal excitation of 0.7 mm amplitude. Results in Fig. 15 are in very good agreement with predictions from eq. (7):

Fig. 9. Z-TVA set up for dynamic tests.

Fig. 10. Input and fast stage force vs. input displacement.

Fig. 11. Gear ratio and stall force vs. temperature.

Fig. 12. Input Stage and Fast Stage position vs. time.

The measured damped frequency is 17.5 ± 0.5 Hz. A damping ratio of 0.18 ± 0.02 is observed. The natural frequency can be then calculated with eq. (25) as:

$$w_n = \frac{w_d}{\sqrt{1 - \xi^2}} = 18 \pm 1 \text{ Hz} \quad (25)$$

In a similar way, the natural frequency of the fast stage can be calculated using eq (17). A natural frequency of 18 Hz can be estimated in very good agreement with the experimental results. The input force has been also measured during the previous tests. A relatively high input force level is observed even at low frequencies due to the friction of the bearings in the input stage. Maximum input force occurs at the resonance of the internal mass. Fig. 16 shows a typical frequency sweep test.

Fig. 13. Input and fast stage speed vs. time.

Fig. 14. Input and fast stage acceleration vs. time.

The input force amplitude vs. excitation frequency is depicted in Fig.17 and compared with the theoretical prediction of eq. (15). Very good agreement is observed, confirming the validity of the proposed model for description of the Z-TVA behavior.

5. Conclusions

A Tuned Vibration Absorber of reduced inertial mass has been designed, manufactured and experimentally demonstrated. This invention, takes advantage of a linear magnetic gear to multiple input vibrations and match impedances between the input stage and the fast moving stage of the gear.

Fig. 15. Normalized Displacement vs. frequency.

Fig. 16. Typical frequency sweep test. Input position and force vs. time.

A detailed dynamic theoretical model of the Z-TVA is proposed and discussed. A case study has been generated and the effectiveness of the Z-TVA is compared to the performance of a classic TVA. Results of this study demonstrate the potential of the technology for highly reduce the mass of tuned vibration absorbers. A prototype of the Z-TVA has been manufactured and tested at component level. Experimental results show a good agreement with the theoretical predictions of the model and confirm the potential of the device to act as a tuned vibration absorber.

A relatively high friction damping was observed in bearings of the input stage. It would be desirable for further development to substitute the sliding friction bearings by linear ball bearings to minimize this friction damping.

Finally, the demonstration of this new technology will allow mechanical engineering from multiple sectors to design optimal performance TVAs with reduced mass and envelope, potentially minimizing manufacturing, installation and maintenance costs.

Fig. 17. Input force vs. frequency ratio. Experimental results and theoretical prediction.

Acknowledgements

This work has been partially funded by the Seventh Framework Clean Sky Program of the EU Commission, under grant number 632492.

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